

PROBLEMATIC ASPECTS AND LEGAL RISKS OF CONCLUDING COPYRIGHT CONTRACTS IN VIRTUAL ENVIRONMENT

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***Summary:** The article deals with the legal problems arising in the conclusion of copyright agreements in the digital environment. It analyses the cases of deviation of user agreements from the requirements established by the legislation, insufficiency of mechanisms for identification of the parties, as well as the risks associated with automatic licensing and transboundary use of works. Special attention is paid to the gaps in the regulatory framework of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the lack of legal regulation of the electronic form of the copyright contract. The comparative approach with international standards, including the provisions of the World Intellectual Property Organisation, allowed to identify key risks and determine the directions of adaptation of national legislation to modern conditions of digital turnover.*

***Keywords:** Copyright contract, digital platform, electronic form, intellectual property, legal risks, cross-border use, WIPO*

The current stage of society's development is characterized by the deep digitalization of all spheres of activity, including intellectual property. One of the central instruments of legal regulation in this area remains the copyright agreement, an agreement through which the author or another copyright holder transfers the rights to use the work. At the same time, the virtualization of transactions and the transition to online contract formats are creating a whole range of new legal challenges.

In the context of the rapid development of digital platforms, cloud storage, online services and online forms of distribution of works, copyright agreements are increasingly concluded remotely, without physical contact between the parties and

often without traditional paper registration. This leads to a number of problems: from the uncertainty of the legal force of electronic agreements to the violation of the rights of authors due to the automatic acceptance of the terms of the platforms and the inability to control the use of their works.

The topic is becoming particularly relevant in the legal system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, where the legal regulation of copyright agreements in the digital environment is still being formed. Despite the existence of general provisions in the Civil Code and the Law on Copyright and Related Rights, practice shows the need for more detailed regulation of the virtual form of contracts, as well as the protection of parties in the context of cross-border and digital offenses.

The purpose of this article is to analyze the problematic aspects of concluding copyright agreements in a virtual environment, identify key legal risks and propose areas for legal improvement, taking into account international standards and the specifics of national legislation.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Copyright and Related Rights" dated July 20, 2006 № 42 was adopted in an era when the main forms of use of works were limited to physical media. Nevertheless, the rapid development of digital platforms, cloud technologies and creative ecosystems has required a rethink of the norms of this law in terms of their applicability to the virtual environment.

Among the provisions potentially covering the digital context, the term "making available" is of particular importance, which includes the transmission of works in such a way that users can access them "from anywhere and at any time of their own choosing." This definition makes it possible to extend the law to the Internet space, including the distribution of works through streaming services, digital art platforms, cloud libraries, and other forms of remote access.

In accordance with article 38 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Copyright and Related Rights", the author's property rights may be transferred to another person solely on the basis of a copyright agreement. This requirement is imperative and does not allow deviations, except in cases expressly provided for.

The Law distinguishes between two main types of copyright agreements:

- an agreement on the transfer of exclusive rights, which grants the right to use the work exclusively to the person specified in the agreement.;
- an agreement on the transfer of non-exclusive rights, allowing parallel use of the work by other entities, including the author himself and a third party.

An analysis of the provisions of the Law shows that it retains the classical model of concluding contracts: author — user (licensee or customer) — physical signature — alienation of rights or transfer of license. In conditions when agreements on the transfer of rights are increasingly concluded in the form of unilateral adherence to the user agreement when uploading a work (for example, on YouTube, TikTok, and ArtStation platforms), a legal gap arises due to the lack of a direct indication of the permissibility of the electronic form of the copyright agreement.¹ In addition, the legislation does not regulate the most important aspects, such as automatic licensing, the specifics of the validity of click agreements, as well as the procedure for proving the will of the parties in cross-border electronic communication.

Thus, it can be concluded that the current version of Law № LRU-42 regarding the regulation of digital transactions with copyright objects requires updating and specification, taking into account new legal risks arising in the online environment.

The potential and limitations of the Civil Code in the context of online copyright agreements. The Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan establishes the principle of freedom of contract (art. 1)², including the right of the parties to independently determine the form, content and method of concluding a transaction, unless otherwise established by law. This provision provides a theoretical basis for recognizing the permissibility of electronic forms of copyright agreements, including those concluded through the interface of a digital platform.

The problem of identifying the parties also plays a significant role. In accordance with Article 19 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a citizen has the right to use a pseudonym, however, in order to recognize a transaction as valid, proper identification is required, especially if it concerns the transfer of property rights. If one of the parties uses an anonymous account or IP address, the possibility of protecting violated rights becomes significantly more difficult.

Along with this, it should be noted that the norms of Articles 8 and 9 of the Civil Code allow for the emergence of civil rights and obligations from actions not directly provided for by law, but arising from its principles. This opens up the possibility of recognizing the legal force of electronic agreements, if there is a

¹ <https://lex.uz/docs/6123336>

² <https://lex.uz/docs/111181>

confirmed expression of will and compliance with the requirements of good faith and reasonableness.

However, the absence of special rules on contractual practice in the digital environment makes the application of the Civil Code fragmented. This creates a high degree of legal uncertainty for authors, users, and digital platforms.

An analysis of the current norms of the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan allows us to conclude that there is a regulatory framework that formally covers the relations of concluding copyright agreements. At the same time, in the context of digitalization, there are clear regulatory gaps, primarily in terms of the form of transactions, identification of the parties and the legal qualification of automatic conditions for digital platforms. To ensure effective legal protection for participants in such legal relations, it is necessary to improve the legislative framework, taking into account international practice and the realities of the virtual economy.

Platform-based user agreements as a substitute for copyright agreements. One of the characteristic phenomena of the digital environment is the substitution of the copyright agreement by the user agreement of the platform (Terms of Use). These agreements are formed in the form of an affiliation agreement and are accepted by the author at the time of uploading the work, however, they do not always meet the requirements of the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan set out in articles 38-39 of the Law "On Copyright and Related Rights" (LRU-42).

For example, by posting a video on the YouTube platform, the user automatically grants a non-exclusive license that allows the content to be used for storage, broadcasting, advertising integrations and modifications. However, such agreements often lack such essential conditions as specific methods of use, the amount and procedure for payment of remuneration, the territory of operation and the permissibility of sublicensing, which makes them legally vulnerable.

Legal practice shows that in the absence of such conditions, an agreement cannot be recognized as a full-fledged copyright agreement, despite the widespread use of it.

Risks of automatic licensing and alienation of rights without control. One of the most controversial aspects of digital agreements is the mechanism of automatic transfer of rights. This is especially evident on resources such as Behance, TikTok, Instagram or GitHub, where, under the terms of user agreements, the author grants

free of charge the right to reproduce, distribute and display content for commercial purposes. This approach contradicts the requirements of article 39 of the LRU-42, according to which all rights not specified in the contract are considered not transferred, and transfer to third parties is allowed only if there is a special condition. Platforms, on the contrary, proceed from the presumption of the widest possible scope of transferred rights, which puts the author in an unequal and often unconscious position.

A separate problem is sublicensing, when a platform can transfer the right to use a work to advertisers, content generation algorithms, or external services (for example, AI integrations) without the author's consent. This creates a situation in which the author not only does not receive remuneration, but also loses the ability to track where and how his work is used.

Cross-border and jurisdictional obstacles. Most digital platforms are registered in the USA, Ireland, Singapore or other jurisdictions with their own copyright regulation. As a result, the Uzbek author who accepted the user agreement is bound by the norms of foreign legislation, including provisions on the choice of applicable law, arbitration and limitation of liability of the platform.

The digital environment imposes completely new requirements on the legal structure of copyright agreements. User agreements, automatic licensing, lack of real control and cross-border barriers create a set of legal risks that the current legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan does not fully cope with. For authors who publish their works on digital platforms, this means loss of control, lack of remuneration, and limited opportunities to protect their rights.

Thus, even if the work is used in violation of rights, the author from Uzbekistan faces the barrier of unavailability of judicial protection, the high cost of conducting business in a foreign jurisdiction and the lack of effective mechanisms to respond to violations. A similar problem arises when trying to identify the violator: the use of pseudonyms, anonymous accounts, and unverified email addresses makes it impossible to bring the perpetrator to justice in a national court.

Ways to improve the legal regulation of copyright contracts in a virtual environment:

1. Legislative adaptation: digital form and standard conditions. To eliminate the above problems, a revision of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Copyright and Related Rights" is necessary. In particular, it is proposed:

- To include a new chapter regulating the conclusion of copyright agreements in electronic form;
- To confirm that an electronic contract can be considered valid if there is a confirmed expression of will (including log files, verification via mail, IP, or EDS);
- To establish mandatory conditions, in the absence of which the user agreement cannot be considered a copyright agreement: the method of use, term, territory, remuneration procedure and indication of sublicensing.

International practice: The EU has a Directive (EU) 2019/790 on the rights of authors in the digital single market (DSM Directive), which obliges platforms to disclose to authors the terms of use and licensing of works.³

2. Digital platforms as subjects of responsibility

It is advisable to introduce a legal qualification of platforms as intermediaries of copyrighted content with a special legal status. Their responsibilities should include:

- storing data on the will of the parties;
- technical verification of the authors;
- providing access to the archive of agreements at the request of the court or law enforcement agencies.

Additionally, it is possible to introduce a voluntary state online register of copyright agreements, operating under the Intellectual Property Agency of Uzbekistan, which allows authors to register the terms of transfer of rights.

3. The need for international legal coordination and the institution of a digital Ombudsman

Given the cross-border nature of the use of works in the digital environment, copyright protection issues cannot be resolved solely by means of national law. It is necessary to build a stable system of international cooperation, primarily with the states where the main digital platforms are registered (USA, EU states, Singapore, etc.).

In this regard, it is necessary to conclude bilateral or multilateral agreements on the recognition of judicial decisions and mutual legal assistance in cases related to copyright infringement on the Internet. Such agreements will ensure real cross-

³ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/790/oj>

border protection of the rights of Uzbek authors whose works are distributed through international digital platforms.

In addition, an electronic complaint mechanism for digital platforms should be developed, including localized forms of copyright infringement notices available on the state portal or at the Intellectual Property Agency. This is especially important for authors who do not speak English and are unable to independently interact with foreign technical support.

It is also necessary to establish an ombudsman for digital rights in the field of intellectual property, with the function of pre-trial dispute resolution between authors and digital intermediaries, monitoring complaints and making recommendations on compliance with licensing transparency.

4. Educational work, law enforcement and standardization of practice

Along with legislative reform and international cooperation, active development of law enforcement and educational infrastructure is required to ensure uniform interpretation of norms and accessibility of legal information for all participants in the digital turnover.

First, it is necessary to ensure the development and publication of standard forms of digital copyright agreements, including templates for licensing agreements, contracts for the creation and use of content adapted to freelance activities. Such templates must be approved by an authorized body and made publicly available on official portals.

Secondly, it requires the formation of a stable judicial practice in the field of copyright in a virtual environment. Methodological recommendations for judges should be prepared, including in cooperation with the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), which regularly organizes the WIPO IP Judges Forum⁴ and provides analytical materials for national law enforcement officials.

Thirdly, a large-scale information and educational program for authors should be implemented, including online guides, interactive platforms and localized licenses similar to the Creative Commons system⁵, explaining the legal nature of exclusive and non-exclusive rights, the specifics of concluding contracts with platforms and ways to protect rights in case of violation.

⁴ <https://www.wipo.int/meetings/en/2024/judgesforum2024.html>

⁵ <https://creativecommons.org/>

The digitalization of copyright relations has revealed significant gaps in the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The current rules do not cover the electronic form of contracts, do not regulate the actions of digital platforms, and do not provide cross-border protection for authors. These problems require a systematic review of the provisions of the Copyright Act, taking into account international standards, in particular, the recommendations of WIPO. Without these changes, ensuring the rights of authors in a virtual environment remains nominal and ineffective.

Rezyume: *Ushbu maqolada mualliflik shartnomalarini raqamli (virtual) muhitda tuzishda yuzaga kelayotgan huquqiy muammolar tahlil qilinadi. Elektron shakldagi bitimlarning yuridik aniqligi, tomonlarni identifikatsiyalashdagi murakkablik, raqamli platformalarda avtomatik litsenziyalash xavflari va asarlarning transchegaraviy tarqatilishi sharoitida mualliflik huquqlarining buzilishi kabi muhim masalalarga e'tibor qaratilgan. O'zbekiston Respublikasi qonunchiligi tahlil qilinib, undagi bo'shliqlar aniqlangan hamda mualliflik huquqlarining virtual tarzda o'tkazilishi bilan bog'liq asosiy huquqiy xavflar aniqlab berilgan. Jahon intellektual mulk tashkiloti (VOIS) doirasida ishlab chiqilgan xalqaro standartlar bilan qiyosiy tahlil asosida milliy qonunchilikni takomillashtirish bo'yicha yo'nalishlar ko'rsatib o'tilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari raqamli sohada intellektual mulk aylanmasi bilan shug'ullanuvchi yuristlar, platforma operatorlari va huquqni muhofaza qiluvchi organlar uchun amaliy ahamiyatga ega.*

Резюме: *В этой статье рассматриваются правовые проблемы, возникающие при заключении авторских договоров в цифровой среде. Особое внимание уделяется неопределённости юридической силы электронных соглашений, сложности идентификации сторон, рискам автоматического лицензирования на цифровых платформах, а также нарушениям авторских прав в условиях трансграничного распространения произведений. Анализируется действующее законодательство Республики Узбекистан, выявляются его пробелы и обозначаются ключевые правовые риски, связанные с виртуальной формой заключения договоров об отчуждении или использовании авторских прав. На основе сопоставления с международными стандартами, включая рекомендации Всемирной организации интеллектуальной собственности (ВОИС), обоснованы направления*

совершенствования национальной правовой базы. Результаты исследования представляют практическую ценность для юристов, операторов цифровых платформ и органов, обеспечивающих защиту прав в сфере интеллектуальной собственности.

Kalit so‘zlar: *mualliflik shartnomasi, raqamli platforma, elektron bitim, intellektual mulk, huquqiy xavflar, transchegaraviy foydalanish, VOIS.*

Ключевые слова: *авторский договор, цифровая платформа, электронная сделка, интеллектуальная собственность, правовые риски, трансграничное использование, ВОИС.*